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Trading Returns for Privacy: Experimental Evidence from Financial Data Leaks

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Abstract

This paper provides benchmark experimental evidence on how individuals trade off financial performance against the risk of disclosing their own financial information when privacy risks are explicit, and outcomes are immediate. In a laboratory investment task with repeated decisions, participants choose between two risky options that differ in expected return and in an explicitly stated probability that choosing one option triggers a pseudonymous disclosure of a limited subset of their pre-elicited financial information to other participants. Participants respond systematically to both return spreads and leak probabilities, but choices are substantially more elastic to financial incentives than to changes in leak risk. In dynamic analyses, experiencing an own leak has modest and short-lived effects, whereas higher leakage among other participants is followed by a lower propensity to select the privacy-risky option. Standard measures of risk and loss aversion and most economic characteristics explain little of the heterogeneity in choices, while context-relevant privacy attitudes are associated with more privacy-protective behavior. Overall, in this transparent-probability benchmark environment, monetary incentives dominate leak risk on average, while social information about others' leaks meaningfully shapes behavior.

Keywords: Privacy preferences; Financial data; Data breaches; Experimental economics

JEL classification: C91; D81; D83; G41; G59

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1 Introduction

The digitalization of economic interactions has dramatically increased the amount of personal information that is collected, stored, and traded. Individuals routinely reveal detailed traces of their consumption, mobility, and social networks in exchange for access to online services or better prices. At the same time, data breaches and leaks have become a recurrent feature of the digital economy, with large-scale incidents regularly exposing the personal information of millions of individuals and imposing non-negligible costs on firms and consumers alike.¹ These developments raise the question of how individuals actually trade off economic benefits against the risk that their personal data may be disclosed.

Financial services provide a particularly salient context for studying this trade-off. Financial data – such as income, wealth, outstanding debt, and detailed payment histories – are among the most sensitive categories of personal information. They are central inputs into credit scoring, fraud detection, and risk management, and they increasingly feed into AI-driven decision systems (Boissay, Ehlers, Gambacorta, & Shin, 2021). Recent policy initiatives such as open banking and, more broadly, open finance seek to promote competition and innovation by facilitating consent-based data sharing between banks, fintechs, and other third parties (OECD, 2023). While these initiatives promise better financial products and improved inclusion, they also multiply the number of actors with access to granular financial data and, therefore, the potential attack surface for data breaches and misuse. Evidence from large credit-reporting and banking incidents suggests that financial data leaks affect individuals’ behavior, for instance by inducing more frequent credit freezes and opt-outs from data sharing (Mikhed & Vogan, 2018). Understanding how individuals value the protection of their financial data, relative to financial returns, is thus crucial for assessing both the welfare effects of data-driven finance and the design of regulatory safeguards.

A large body of literature in economics and related fields has studied how individuals value privacy and how they behave when their data may be collected or shared. Theoretical and empirical work has emphasized the idea of a “privacy calculus,” in which individuals trade off expected benefits and perceived privacy costs, as well as the so-called “privacy paradox,” whereby stated concerns about privacy often coexist with seemingly lax disclosure behavior. This literature has documented the role of incomplete information, behavioral biases, and contextual framing in shaping privacy-related decisions. However, most experimental evidence focuses on relatively generic online data (such as browsing histories or social network profiles), often in static environments where privacy risks are only partially specified. Much less is known about how individuals behave when the data at stake are financial, when the probabilities of a data leak are transparent, and when decisions are repeated over time with feedback.

Most privacy calculus models implicitly assume transparent and well-defined probabilities over privacy outcomes, and decision makers who can weigh these probabilities against expected benefits. In practice, individuals often face severe uncertainty and ambiguity over whether and how their data may be leaked or abused, and rely on heuristics and boundedly rational strategies. Within such environments, observed choices may diverge sharply from stated concerns and intentions. In this paper, I study privacy decisions in a dynamic financial environment in which the probabilities of data leaks are made explicit to participants and leak outcomes are realized in real time. This choice is consistent with standard experimental protocols that avoid deception, and it also serves a methodological purpose: it allows us to isolate how individuals trade off financial returns and privacy risks when the relevant probabilities are clearly stated and stable. I view this setting as a benchmark, abstracting from some of the uncertainty and opacity that characterise real-world data environments.

In real-world data environments, individuals rarely know the likelihood, timing, or audience of

a potential leak. To isolate the privacy calculus under well-defined risks, I study decisions in a benchmark laboratory setting in which leak probabilities are explicitly stated, and outcomes are realized immediately. Leaks are deliberately limited in scope and disclosed pseudonymously to other participants, so the paper speaks to behavior under transparent and immediate (but stylized) privacy risks rather than to a universal valuation of privacy across contexts.

I design a dynamic investment task in which participants repeatedly allocate an endowment between a safe option and a risky option. The task is explicitly framed as an investment decision: in each round, subjects choose between two risky investment opportunities and decide how much of their endowment to invest in the selected option. Across rounds, the risky option varies along two dimensions: its expected financial return and the probability that choosing it will trigger a leak of the participant’s own financial data. Leaks consist in revealing to other participants a subset of the subject’s confidential financial information collected in a pre-experimental questionnaire (income, assets, debts, and other indicators). Leak probabilities are explicitly displayed, and outcomes (financial payoffs and data leaks) are realized immediately after each decision. This design allows us to separately identify how choices respond to financial incentives and to the risk of a data leak in a dynamic financial context with transparent and time-varying probabilities of real-time data leaks.

This paper documents three benchmark facts in this transparent-probability design. First, participants trade off returns and leak risk in the expected directions, but the response to return spreads is much larger than the response to leak probabilities, indicating an asymmetric sensitivity to financial versus privacy incentives in this setting. Second, the dynamic effects of leaks differ by source: own leaks have modest and short-lived impacts, whereas greater leakage among other participants is followed by a lower propensity to choose the privacy-risky option, consistent with a social-information (or “crowd”) channel. Third, standard economic preference measures (including risk and loss aversion) and most economic characteristics explain little of the heterogeneity in choices, while context-relevant privacy attitudes are more predictive. Taken together, the results clarify which behavioral patterns emerge when privacy risks are immediate, probabilities are explicit, and decisions are repeated with feedback.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the related literature and derives testable hypotheses about the trade-off between financial returns and data leaks, the role of personal versus others’ leaks, and the impact of individual characteristics. Section 3 describes the experimental design and procedures. Section 4 presents the main empirical results on choices, dynamics, and heterogeneity. Section 5 discusses the implications of the findings for data-driven financial services and privacy regulation, and Section 6 concludes.

2 Related literature

2.1 Definitions, subjectivity, and the economics of privacy

A large interdisciplinary literature has emphasized that privacy is a multi-dimensional and fundamentally subjective concept. Philosophers, legal scholars and social scientists have alternately defined privacy as the protection of a personal sphere or “right to be let alone” (Warren & Brandeis, 1989), control over personal information and its disclosure (Westin, 1968), the regulation of boundaries between self and others and between private, shared, and public domains (Altman, 1975), or as a precondition for dignity, autonomy, and individual freedom (Schoeman, 1992). Economic approaches have stressed the role of privacy in governing the flow of information in markets and organizations, with attention to strategic disclosure and concealment in personal and business contexts (Posner, 1978).

Building on these foundations, a specific field of privacy economics has emerged, distinct from classical information economics. While information economics typically examines the value of information per se, privacy economics focuses on information about identifiable individuals and on how such information is collected, processed, shared, and monetized (?). Because privacy concerns and attitudes are context-dependent and idiosyncratic, individuals exhibit a wide range of behaviors and strategies when deciding whether to share or protect data (Morando, Iemma, & Raiteri, 2014; Nissenbaum, 2004). This diversity reflects heterogeneous concerns about the accessibility of personal data, social and organizational threats, and the perceived sensitivity of different data types (Krasnova, Günther, Spiekermann, & Koroleva, 2009). This experiment contributes to this literature by focusing specifically on financial data, which previous work identifies as particularly sensitive and consequential for individuals' economic opportunities (Mothersbaugh, Foxx, Beatty, & Wang, 2012; Carrascal, Riederer, Erramilli, Cherubini, & De Oliveira, 2013).

2.2 The privacy paradox and privacy calculus

Despite rising awareness of privacy risks, many empirical studies document a disconnect between stated privacy concerns and actual disclosure behavior, a phenomenon often referred to as the "privacy paradox" (Berendt, Günther, & Spiekermann, 2005; Norberg, Horne, & Horne, 2007). Survey and experimental evidence shows that individuals frequently express strong concerns about the misuse of their personal data while simultaneously engaging in behaviors that expose substantial amounts of information (Acquisti & Gross, 2006; Norberg et al., 2007; Turow, King, Hoofnagle, Bleakley, & Hennessy, 2009). Yet there is no consensus on whether this disconnect truly reflects inconsistent preferences or instead arises from measurement and contextual issues.

One influential line of work argues that the paradox may partly be an artefact of comparing broad attitudinal measures with highly specific behaviors. Attitudes are often elicited in general terms (e.g., "I am concerned about my online privacy"), whereas behaviors are observed in concrete, context-rich situations. As a result, weak or noisy correlations between concerns and behavior may not imply irrationality, but rather the limitations of global measures as predictors of situational choices (?). Other contributions emphasize that individuals may hold stable preferences but face complex trade-offs between privacy and other goals, leading to context-dependent decisions.

These trade-offs are captured by the notion of a *privacy calculus*, according to which individuals mentally weigh anticipated losses of privacy against potential benefits of data disclosure (Laufer & Wolfe, 1977; Culnan & Armstrong, 1999; Dinev & Hart, 2006; H. J. Smith, Milberg, & Burke, 1996). Empirical work has documented such trade-offs in a variety of settings, showing that individuals are willing to disclose more data in exchange for price reductions, personalization, convenience, or social benefits (Dinev & Hart, 2006; Jiang, Heng, & Choi, 2013; Xu, Luo, Carroll, & Rosson, 2011; Lee & Kwon, 2015). Importantly, the privacy calculus framework accommodates the possibility that individuals may continue to express concerns about privacy while nonetheless choosing to disclose data when perceived benefits outweigh expected costs. In this perspective, sharing information does not automatically equate to a loss of privacy, nor does complete concealment guarantee optimal outcomes. Studies in online and e-commerce environments illustrate that consumers may pay premiums to transact with privacy-protective merchants, display growing concerns over time, adopt privacy-seeking behaviors, or resort to obfuscation strategies while still participating actively in digital markets (Boyd & Marwick, 2011; Goldfarb & Tucker, 2012; Kang, Brown, & Kiesler, 2013; Rainie et al., 2013; Stutzman, Gross, & Acquisti, 2013; Tsai, Egelman, Cranor, & Acquisti, 2011; Jentzsch, Preibusch, & Harasser, 2012; Preibusch, Kübler, & Beresford, 2013).

2.3 Uncertainty, bounded rationality, and limits of the privacy calculus

The privacy calculus literature typically assumes decision makers who are informed about the relevant risks and can form (possibly subjective) probabilities over privacy outcomes. In practice, however, privacy outcomes are often uncertain in a stronger sense: individuals may be unaware that data are being collected at all, may not know which entities have access to their information, and may have little understanding of how data will be processed or reused (Wakefield, 2013). This context is closer to Knightian uncertainty (Knight, 1921) than to risk: probabilities of breaches, secondary uses, or identity theft are neither known nor easily knowable.

These informational frictions open the door to systematic deviations from the predictions of a fully informed privacy calculus. A growing body of work documents the role of heuristics, framing effects, present bias, and other cognitive limitations in privacy-related decisions (Acquisti, Grossklags, & et al., 2007; Knijnenburg & Kobsa, 2013; Frik & Mittone, 2019; Acquisti, 2014). Bounded rationality (Acquisti & Grossklags, 2005) and limited attention may further lead individuals to underweight low-probability but high-impact privacy risks, or to focus on salient immediate benefits instead. From this perspective, observed inconsistencies between concerns and behavior may reflect not only contextual specificity, but also structural features of the decision environment: complexity, opacity, delayed consequences, and asymmetric information.

The experimental design deliberately abstracts from several of these sources of uncertainty. Rather than attempting to reproduce the full complexity of real-world data flows, I construct a setting in which the probabilities of data leaks are clearly stated, stable over time, and realized immediately after each decision. This simplification is partly dictated by standard experimental requirements of transparency and non-deception, but it also serves a methodological purpose: it creates a benchmark environment that is relatively favourable to the privacy calculus view. If individuals are ever in a position to perform informed trade-offs between financial returns and privacy risks, it is arguably in such a context. Behaviour in this simplified setting therefore provides an upper bound on the weight that individuals place on privacy risks when informational frictions and ambiguity are minimised.

2.4 Data leaks, financial information, and economic trade-offs

A distinct strand of literature examines data breaches, identity theft, and the economics of information security. Empirical work shows that the probability distributions of breach incidents and the subsequent misuse of stolen information are highly uncertain and difficult to communicate to consumers (Mann, 2015; Solove, 2005). From the consumer standpoint, insufficient awareness and inadequate protection of personal data can be interpreted as “insecurity” in Solove’s taxonomy, capturing failures to prevent leaks and unauthorized access (Solove, 2005). Within an economic framework, however, such insecurity may itself be the outcome of a trade-off between privacy and other objectives.

Payment system models developed by Roberds and Schreft (2009) and Kahn and Roberds (2008) illustrate these trade-offs in financial contexts. In Roberds and Schreft (2009), privacy losses from identity theft are weighed against the benefits of broad access to credit and efficient payment networks. Similarly, Kahn and Roberds (2008) analyze the tension between the desire to avoid intrusive monitoring of individuals and the need to combat transaction fraud. In both cases, some degree of privacy risk may persist even as technology improves, because eliminating it completely would require costly monitoring or restrictions that themselves reduce welfare. These models highlight that privacy losses and security failures can arise as an equilibrium outcome of economic incentives, rather than solely from poor design or lack of awareness.

This study contributes to this literature by implementing data leaks involving sensitive financial information in an experimental setting with known probability distributions. Participants face repeated decisions in which one option offers higher expected financial returns at the cost of an explicit risk that their own income, assets, debts, or other financial indicators will be revealed to peers. This allows us to observe directly how individuals trade off financial performance against the risk of a financial data leak, and to compare these trade-offs with the qualitative predictions of the above models. In contrast to the complex and opaque environments typically studied in observational work on data breaches, this experiment isolates the impact of transparent leak probabilities and immediate leak realizations on behavior.

2.5 Social influences and individual heterogeneity in privacy decisions

An emerging body of research points to the importance of social influences and individual heterogeneity in privacy behavior. Social norms, peer actions, and the visibility of others' experiences (such as being hacked or suffering a data leak) can affect both perceived risks and acceptable levels of disclosure (Krasnova et al., 2009; Nissenbaum, 2004). Yet relatively few experimental studies have explicitly investigated how observing others' privacy losses shapes one's own willingness to take privacy risks.

The experimental design addresses this gap by distinguishing between personal and others' leaks. Participants not only experience leaks of their own financial data but also observe when leaks affect other participants. This feature enables us to evaluate whether social spillovers—captured by aggregate leak events in previous rounds—have a distinct effect on subsequent investment choices over and above individual experiences. I thus connect the economics of privacy with broader experimental literatures on social learning, externalities, and moral or social preferences, in which observing harm to others can modify willingness to take risks or impose externalities.

Finally, this study relates privacy behavior to individual characteristics such as risk and loss aversion, financial situation, digital literacy, and psychometric measures of privacy concerns and attitudes. Prior work suggests that factors such as trust, perceived control, and information sensitivity shape privacy decisions (Dinev & Hart, 2006; Xu et al., 2011; Mothersbaugh et al., 2012). At the same time, global measures of privacy concern have often shown limited predictive power for concrete behaviors, feeding the debate on the privacy paradox (Dienlin & Trepte, 2015). By combining standard elicitation tasks (for risk and loss aversion) with a detailed financial questionnaire, a digital knowledge assessment, and psychometric scales adapted from Dienlin and Trepte (2015), I can assess to what extent context-specific perceptions—such as the perceived riskiness and sensitivity of the financial data at stake—better explain observed choices than broad attitudinal measures.

2.6 Research questions and hypotheses

The experiment and main analyses were pre-registered on AsPredicted (ID #154386).² Guided by the literature reviewed above and by this pre-analysis plan, the empirical work is structured around the following research questions and hypotheses.

First, I ask to what extent individuals trade off financial returns against transparent risks of leaking their own financial data in a dynamic setting. The privacy calculus framework implies that higher expected financial returns should increase the propensity to select the option carrying a privacy risk, whereas higher probabilities of a data leak should decrease it. Accordingly, the first hypothesis is:

Hypothesis 1 (Financial return and leak risk) *The probability that a subject chooses the option involving a potential data leak increases in its expected return relative to the safe option and decreases in the probability of a data leak.*

Second, I investigate how experimental conditions that exogenously modify the relative attractiveness of the privacy-risky option affect behavior. The induced-value treatments systematically shift the expected return of the option carrying the data leak risk while keeping risk and leak probabilities comparable. This leads to the second hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2 (Induced values of privacy risk) *For a given leak probability and baseline spread, subjects in the positive induced-value treatment are more likely to choose the option involving a potential data leak than subjects in the no induced-value condition, while subjects in the negative induced-value treatment are less likely to do so.*

Third, I study how data leak events affect subsequent choices over time. The design allows us to distinguish leaks affecting a given subject from leaks affecting other participants. Economic models of information security suggest that the perceived cost of a leak depends on the magnitude of the incident (Solove, 2005; Roberds & Schreft, 2009; Kahn & Roberds, 2008). Building on the idea that experienced loss and salient social information can shape risk-taking and externality-imposing behavior, I formulate:

Hypothesis 3 (Personal leaks versus magnitude of leaks) *Experiencing a leak of one’s own financial data reduces, at least temporarily, the probability of choosing the privacy-risky option in subsequent rounds. Observing leaks affecting other participants also reduces this probability, and may have a distinct or stronger effect than personal leaks.*

Finally, I analyze how individual characteristics shape privacy-related decisions in this environment. The literature highlights the importance of risk and loss aversion, financial situation, digital literacy, and privacy attitudes for disclosure behavior (Dinev & Hart, 2006; Xu et al., 2011; Dienlin & Trepte, 2015). The pre-registered analyses include the predictive power of such measures for behavior in the investment task. I thus state:

Hypothesis 4 (Individual heterogeneity) *Higher risk aversion, greater perceived sensitivity and riskiness of the financial data at stake, and stronger context-specific privacy concerns are associated with a lower propensity to choose the privacy-risky option, whereas broad, generic measures of privacy concern have limited predictive power for behavior in the experiment.*

These hypotheses structure the empirical analysis that follows, in terms of both overall trade-offs between financial returns and privacy risk and the dynamic, social, and heterogeneous dimensions of privacy-related decision-making.

3 Experimental design and procedures

3.1 Allocation decision task

The core of the experiment is an allocation decision task comprising 60 rounds. Table 1 summarizes the key experimental parameters. In each round, participants received an endowment of 100 experimental currency units (ECUs) and decided how much of this endowment to allocate to one of two investment options. In the written instructions, both options were explicitly described as

Table 1: Experimental design at a glance

Element	Value
Participants	186 participants (laboratory sessions).
Main task	60 rounds. Each round: endowment of 100 ECUs; choose between Options A and B; choose the fraction of the endowment to invest (uninvested amount yields 0).
Payoffs	Each option has three states (optimistic/realistic/pessimistic) with probabilities 25%/50%/25%. Within a round, the two options have the same payoff standard deviation; they differ only in expected return and privacy risk. Payoffs drawn from 30 scenarios.
Return spread	Difference in expected return (percentage points) varies across rounds: 0–5 p.p. (low), 5–10 p.p. (medium), >10 p.p. (high).
Privacy risk	In each round, exactly one option carries a leak probability $p_{\text{leak}} \in \{0, 5, \dots, 40\}\%$; the other option has $p_{\text{leak}} = 0$. If a leak occurs, it is realized immediately after the monetary outcome.
Leak content & audience	Leak reveals to other participants in the session: pseudonym and age + two randomly drawn items from seven pre-elicited financial indicators (income, financial wealth, real estate wealth, indebtedness status, indebtedness level, saving capacity, rental situation).
Treatments	Between-subject: Baseline; +4 p.p. shift in expected return of the leak option; –4 p.p. shift.
Payment	One round randomly selected for payment; conversion rate 12.5 ECUs per €1.

risky investment opportunities (Options A and B), and the task as choosing an investment and the amount to invest.³ Following Gneezy and Potters (1997), participants chose the fraction of the endowment to invest in the selected option, while any non-invested amount yielded no return. This feature limits the scope for trivial “opt-out” behavior driven purely by loss aversion.

Each option consisted of three possible states of nature—optimistic, realistic, and pessimistic—with fixed probabilities of 25%, 50%, and 25%, respectively. Each state yielded a monetary payoff, so that expected returns differed across options. The decision interface, which was presented as an investment screen, displayed for each option the three payoffs and their probabilities, the expected payoff (average return), and the difference in expected payoff between the two options, expressed in percentage points, exactly as described in the instructions (Table 10). The two options within a round always shared the same standard deviation, ensuring comparable financial risk profiles. The only differences between the options were their expected returns and the presence of a privacy risk: in each round, one option was associated with a strictly positive probability that the participant’s financial data would be leaked, while the other option was free of such risk.

The payoffs for both options were drawn from a set of 30 distinct scenarios. These scenarios were constructed so that, across the 60 rounds, the option involving a potential data leak financially dominated the safe option in exactly half of the cases and was dominated in the other half. This symmetry ensures that participants faced both financially attractive and unattractive privacy-risky options in equal proportions.

Throughout the task, I varied the spread in expected returns between the two options. This spread serves as a measure of the financial compensation offered for accepting the privacy risk and can be interpreted as a proxy for participants’ willingness to accept potential externalities induced by data leaks. The 30 scenarios were designed to span three levels of spread, expressed in percentage points: 10 scenarios with a low spread (between 0 and 5 p.p.), 10 with a medium spread (between

5 and 10 p.p.), and 10 with a high spread (above 10 p.p.).

The order of scenario presentation was randomly determined at the session level and kept identical for all participants within a session, as were the associated leak probabilities (see below). Thus, all participants within a session faced the same sequence of financial and privacy-risk profiles. After each round, participants received immediate feedback on the realized state and the resulting payoff. At the end of the experiment, one round was randomly selected for payment, with a conversion rate of 12.5 ECUs per euro.

3.2 Experimental treatments

Participants were randomly assigned to one of three between-subjects treatments summarized in Table 2. In all treatments, participants first completed a socio-demographic and financial questionnaire, as well as two incentivized tasks (Section 3.4). The treatments differed only in the induced value attached to the option carrying the privacy risk, in line with the induced-values framework of V. L. Smith (1976). This variation modifies financial incentives while preserving the structure of privacy risks.

In the baseline treatment, expected returns were determined solely by the 30 payoff scenarios described above. Treatment 1 added a systematic positive shift of 4 percentage points to the expected return of the option involving a potential data leak, whereas Treatment 2 applied a systematic negative shift of 4 percentage points to that option. This manipulation creates exogenous variation in the financial attractiveness of the privacy-risky option and allows us to study how stronger or weaker financial compensation affects the willingness to accept privacy risk.

To maintain comparability across treatments, I imposed a simple rule on expected return differences when the privacy-risky option financially dominated the safe option. In the baseline treatment, the average difference in expected returns in such cases was 8 p.p.; in Treatment 1 and Treatment 2, the corresponding averages were 12 p.p. and 4 p.p., respectively.

Table 2: Treatment overview

Condition	Induced value for the data-leak option
Baseline	None
Treatment 1	Systematic and positive
Treatment 2	Systematic and negative

Notes. This table reports the between-subjects treatment conditions. Sample sizes per condition are indicated in Figure 1.

3.3 Implementation of data leaks

Implementing data leaks in a laboratory environment raises both ethical and methodological challenges. In the design, the probability of a data leak is framed as an attribute of the investment options: for each decision interface, one of the two risky investments carries a strictly positive probability that some of the investor’s financial data will be disclosed, while the other investment is leak-free. In line with standard practices that avoid deception in economic experiments (Friedman & Sunder, 1994), all features of the data leaks were fully disclosed to participants before the start of the study. The primary objective was to examine how transparent risk probabilities, combined with financial incentives, shape privacy-related decisions. I therefore deliberately prioritized perfect information over real-world ambiguity.

In the original design, both the volume and the content of leaked data were to be randomly determined, in an attempt to mimic real-world uncertainty. To satisfy ethical constraints while preserving internal validity, I adopted a “degraded” leak implementation in the final design. Leaks were restricted to a subset of the data collected in the initial financial questionnaire, thereby reducing their potential impact while maintaining the essential structure of the privacy risk.

The final protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Board⁴ (IRB) associated with the Laboratoire d’Économie Expérimentale de Paris⁵ (LEEP). In the implemented design, a leak consisted of revealing to other participants the subject’s pseudonym, age, and two data items drawn at random from a pool of seven financial indicators: declared annual income, financial wealth, real estate wealth, indebtedness status, level of indebtedness, saving capacity, and rental situation. Focusing on purely economic variables follows Mothersbaugh et al. (2012) and Carrascal et al. (2013), who show that information sensitivity matters for disclosure decisions and that financial and offline data tend to be perceived as more sensitive and more valuable than many online traces.

The probabilities of data leaks were determined at the session level by randomly drawing 30 values and associating them with the 30 payoff scenarios, before generating symmetric counterparts as described in Section 3.1. The leak probability parameter, denoted p_{leak} , took values between 0% and 40%, in 5 percentage point increments. These values were then held fixed across participants within a session. In each round where $p_{leak} > 0$, choosing the option associated with the privacy risk implied that the participant faced the stated probability that a leak would occur immediately after the financial outcome was realized.

Collecting sensitive financial data raises additional concerns about social desirability and misreporting. Sensitive questions about income and wealth, in particular, are prone to both underreporting and overreporting, as documented in survey research (Moore & Welniak, 2000; Angel, Disslbacher, Humer, & Schnetzer, 2019; Bound, Brown, & Mathiowetz, 2001). To mitigate these issues, I implemented a two-step data collection procedure. The financial questionnaire used to elicit the variables that could later be leaked was first administered as a pre-registration questionnaire prior to the lab session. The same questions were then asked again at the beginning of the experiment. Discrepancies between the two sets of answers were used ex post as a control for potential misreporting in the econometric analysis.

3.4 Questionnaires and additional tasks

Before entering the allocation decision task, all participants completed a comprehensive financial questionnaire designed to mirror standard data collection practices in the financial industry, in line with the MiFID II directive.⁶ The questionnaire covered socio-demographic characteristics, income and wealth, indebtedness, rental status, savings behavior, and self-reported financial knowledge and experience. As noted above, these data served both as potential leak content and as controls in the analysis.

The questionnaire also included two incentivized tasks to elicit preferences over risk and losses. Risk attitudes were measured using the multiple price list design of Holt and Laury (2002) (Figure 6 in the Appendix), while loss aversion was measured using a simple lottery choice task adapted from Gächter, Johnson, and Herrmann (2022) (Figure 8 in the Appendix). Payoffs from these tasks were realized at the end of the experiment. Summary statistics for the elicited preference parameters are reported in Appendix A.2.

At the end of the main task, participants completed two additional questionnaires. The first was a digital knowledge test based on EuroPass materials,⁷ which I use as a proxy for digital literacy in the analysis. The second was a psychometric questionnaire adapted from Dienlin and Trepte (2015), extended with additional items tailored to the experimental context. This instrument captures

multiple dimensions of privacy, including informational, social, and psychological aspects, as well as participants’ perceived risk of data leaks and self-reported privacy-related behaviors. Detailed wording, response scales, and aggregation procedures for these items are provided in Appendix A.3.

3.5 Recruitment and data collection procedures

The experiment was conducted at the LEEP, the experimental economics laboratory of Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne and the Paris School of Economics. Participants were recruited from the laboratory’s pool of volunteers. To limit age-related heterogeneity, individuals older than 50 were not invited. Sessions took place in December 2023; experimental data were collected between 8 and 22 December 2023.

Upon arrival, participants received written instructions and accessed the experimental software, which was implemented in oTree (Chen, Schonger, & Wickens, 2016), using personal identifiers created at the pre-registration stage. After completing the pre-registration financial questionnaire and the two incentivized preference tasks, participants were reminded of the nature of the data leaks and informed that participation was voluntary and could be discontinued at any time. None of the 186 enrolled participants chose to withdraw, and all provided explicit informed consent.

The main allocation task then started, followed by the digital knowledge and psychometric questionnaires. Throughout, I implemented strict data handling procedures to ensure that experimental data remained pseudonymous and that only approved variables could appear in potential leaks. The experiment was conducted in French and lasted on average 90 minutes. Participants received an average payment of €16.09 (SD = 3.77), approximately US\$17.78 at the exchange rate prevailing at the end of December 2023.⁸ Figure 1 summarizes the sequence of tasks and the timing of information and outcomes.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the experiment

4 Results

4.1 Sample descriptives

A total of 186 participants took part in the experiment. On average, they were 28.19 years old (SD = 7.63), and 51.07% were male. In terms of annual income, 56.45% reported earning between 0 and 10,000 euros, 16.12% between 10,000 and 25,000 euros, 22.58% between 25,000 and 45,000 euros, 3.22% between 45,000 and 60,000 euros, and 1.7% above 60,000 euros. Regarding education, 44.62% held a Master’s degree, 36.55% an undergraduate degree or BTEC Higher National Diploma, and 16.12% a secondary degree. Students constituted the majority of the sample (56.99%), followed by employees (16.66%), white-collar and highly qualified workers (10.75%), intermediate professions (6.45%), other occupations (5.37%), and craftsmen, shopkeepers, and business owners (3.76%).

To assess the quality of the financial and socio-demographic data, I compare answers given in the pre-registration questionnaire and in the in-lab questionnaire. For variables not eligible for leaks (age, gender, marital status, number of children, socio-professional category, education level, and postal code), the average consistency ratio is 96.39% (SD = 8.47). For variables that can be

included in data leaks (see Section 3.3), the average consistency ratio is 82.53% (SD = 15.11); the difference in the distribution of the two ratios is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Allowing for a 2.5% deviation above and below, the specific consistency ratio is 83.33% (SD = 14.85). On average, participants spent 63.80 minutes on the main allocation task across sessions. Additional summary statistics and details on completion times are reported in the Appendix.

In the remainder of this section, I first study participants’ allocation decisions in the investment task, focusing on the trade-off between expected returns and the risk of a data leak. I then examine the role of leak realizations over time and the influence of individual characteristics, including psychometric measures of privacy attitudes and self-reported perceptions of risk.

4.2 Main trade-off between financial returns and privacy risk

4.2.1 Descriptive evidence: spreads and leak probabilities

I begin by providing descriptive evidence on how participants trade off expected financial returns against the probability of a data leak in the investment task. In this subsection, I focus on rounds in which the option carrying the data leak risk financially dominates the safe option in terms of expected returns, so that choosing the safe option entails a (pure) privacy premium.

Figure 2: Average allocation choice in the risky option for personal data

Notes. Panel (a) depicts the average allocation rate to the option carrying the data leak risk by spread category, conditional on this option dominating the safe one in terms of expected returns. Panel (b) shows the average allocation rate to the same option by probability level of the data leak risk. Rounds with $p_{leak} = 0$ are excluded in Panel (a) and included in Panel (b). Error bars indicate standard errors of the mean (SEM). p -values are based on logistic regressions of the binary allocation choice on spread (Panel a; $n = 5231$) and leak-probability categories (Panel b; $n = 5910$), with standard errors clustered at the participant level.

Result 1 (Trade-off between expected returns and leak risk). *Participants’ allocation decisions respond systematically to both the spread in expected returns and the probability of a data leak, consistent with a privacy–return trade-off in the investment task.*

Support: Panel (a) of Figure 2 shows, for rounds in which the “leak” option offers a higher

expected return than the safe option and $p_{leak} > 0$, the fraction of rounds in which participants allocate a positive amount of their endowment to the leak option. The underlying estimates come from a logistic regression of the binary allocation choice on indicators for the three spread categories ($n = 5231$; robust standard errors clustered at the participant level). When the spread in expected returns between the leak and the safe option is low (0–5 percentage points), the average allocation rate to the leak option is 58.93%. This rate increases sharply with the spread: it reaches 88.61% in the Medium spread condition (AME = 0.221, $p < 0.001$) and 92.97% in the High spread condition (AME = 0.270, $p < 0.001$). The difference between the Medium and High spread conditions is also statistically significant (AME = 0.072, $p < 0.001$). In the investment frame of the task, participants are thus much more willing to accept the possibility of a data leak when the associated option offers a sufficiently higher expected monetary return.

Panel (b) of Figure 2 documents how the leak probability affects choices in rounds where the leak option dominates the safe one. Here I group rounds by the level of p_{leak} and report the fraction of allocations to the leak option within each group, based on a logistic regression of the binary allocation choice on leak-probability categories ($n = 5910$; clustered standard errors). When $p_{leak} = 0$, i.e. when no privacy risk is present, 95.14% of choices go to the option with the highest expected return. As the probability of a data leak increases, the allocation rate to the leak option declines monotonically: to 83.46% for $p_{leak} \in \{5, 10\}\%$ (AME = -0.249 , $p < 0.001$), 80.28% for $p_{leak} \in \{15, 20\}\%$ (AME = -0.290 , $p < 0.001$), 80.19% for $p_{leak} \in \{25, 30\}\%$ (AME = -0.299 , $p < 0.001$), and 68.85% for $p_{leak} \in \{35, 40\}\%$ (AME = -0.431 , $p < 0.001$). Even in this transparent environment, higher leak probabilities therefore discourage investment in the privacy-risky option.

Figure 3 combines spreads and leak probabilities and confirms that both dimensions matter jointly. When the spread is below 5 percentage points, participants tend to allocate more often to the safe option, regardless of the probability of a leak. For intermediate spreads (between 5 and 10 percentage points), there is a marked shift toward the safe option when p_{leak} exceeds 25%. At higher spreads (above roughly 15 percentage points), average allocation rates to the leak option become more uniform and generally high, suggesting that, beyond a certain return premium, potential gains from the leak option largely outweigh concerns about privacy risk for most participants.

Finally, Figure 4 contrasts choices across dominance relations. Panel (a) shows that the average allocation rate to the safe option when it offers the higher expected return is systematically higher than the average allocation rate to the leak option when *it* offers the higher expected return, within each spread category. In other words, participants react more strongly to financial dominance when it is aligned with privacy protection than when it requires accepting a data leak risk. Panel (b) shows that, conditional on choosing a given option, the average invested amount is broadly similar across scenarios, except in the High spread condition, where participants allocate significantly more when the safe option dominates than when the leak option dominates ($t(3009.6) = -5.0106$, $p < 0.001$). Taken together, these patterns suggest that participants take the privacy dimension into account when deciding whether to invest in the leak option, but that, once this discrete choice is made, the intensive margin of how much to invest is less sensitive to the presence of privacy risk.

Overall, the descriptive evidence in this subsection supports a systematic trade-off between expected financial returns and the probability of a data leak in the dynamic investment task. Participants are more likely to choose the privacy-risky option when the return premium is large and less likely to do so as the leak probability rises, providing a first, reduced-form validation of Hypothesis 1.

Figure 3: Heatmap of average allocation to the risky option for personal data

Notes. The figure illustrates the average allocation rate to the option carrying the data leak risk across combinations of leak-probability levels and spread categories, conditional on this option dominating the safe one in terms of expected returns ($n = 5910$). Horizontal lines indicate the distinct spread parametrizations introduced in Section 3.1.

4.2.2 Econometric evidence: spread, leak probability, and treatments

Result 2 (Financial performance versus privacy protection). *When the option carrying the data leak risk weakly dominates the safe option in terms of expected return, participants' allocation decisions respond to both the leak probability and the return spread, but are substantially more sensitive to the latter, indicating that financial performance tends to outweigh privacy concerns.*

Support: Table 3 reports logit estimates of the probability of allocating to the option carrying the data leak risk, separately by treatment (Models 1–3) and for the pooled sample (Models 4–5). The estimation sample is restricted to rounds in which (i) the leak probability is strictly positive and (ii) the option carrying the data leak risk weakly dominates the safe option in terms of expected return (non-negative spread). The first restriction ensures that a privacy trade-off is always present, so that the coefficient on leak probability can be interpreted as capturing how changes in an existing leak risk are associated with changes in the log-odds of choosing the risky option, rather than the discrete jump from no risk to some risk. The second restriction excludes rounds in which the leak

Figure 4: Average allocation choice and allocation level

Notes. Panel (a) compares the average allocation rate to the leak option when it dominates the safe option in terms of expected returns ($N = 5231$) with the average allocation rate to the safe option when it dominates the leak option ($N = 4571$), by spread category. Panel (b) compares the corresponding average allocation levels (conditional on investing). Error bars indicate standard errors of the mean (SEM). p -values are based on two-sided Mann–Whitney U tests.

option is strictly dominated in expected return, where almost all participants allocate to the safe option by construction and variation in choices is largely mechanical.

Across all specifications, the standardized spread variable enters with a positive and highly significant coefficient, while the standardized leak probability enters with a negative and significant coefficient. In the baseline condition (Model 1), a one-standard deviation increase in the spread is associated with an increase of 0.856 in the log-odds of choosing the leak option, whereas a one-standard deviation increase in the leak probability reduces the log-odds by 0.442. In the pooled specification with controls (Model 5), the coefficient on spread rises to 1.577, compared with -0.236 for the leak probability. In terms of odds ratios, this implies that a one-standard deviation increase in the spread multiplies the odds of choosing the leak option by roughly 4.8, while a one-standard deviation increase in the leak probability reduces those odds by about 21%.

The same qualitative pattern holds within each treatment arm. In the positive induced-value treatment (Model 2), the coefficient on spread (1.776) is more than seven times larger in absolute value than the coefficient on the leak probability (-0.225), and in the negative induced-value treatment (Model 3), the spread coefficient (1.400) likewise dominates the probability coefficient (-0.119). Adding socio-demographic and literacy controls in the pooled specification (Model 5) leaves the magnitudes of both coefficients essentially unchanged, suggesting that neither composition effects nor observable individual characteristics are driving these relationships. These results show that, within the domain where the leak-bearing option offers at least as high an expected return as the safe option, participants do react to higher leak probabilities by allocating less often to the risky option, but their behavior is much more elastic with respect to financial incentives. This pattern is consistent with the privacy calculus framework: participants tend to accept that

Table 3: Determinants of Allocation Choices: Experimental Parameters

	<i>Dependent variable: Data Leak Allocation</i>				
	Baseline (1)	Treatment 1 (+) (2)	Treatment 2 (-) (3)	Pooled (4)	Pooled (5)
Spread (Std.)	0.856*** (0.221)	1.776*** (0.309)	1.400*** (0.242)	1.481*** (0.178)	1.577*** (0.177)
Probability (Std.)	-0.442*** (0.079)	-0.225*** (0.065)	-0.119* (0.056)	-0.219*** (0.041)	-0.236*** (0.043)
Treatment 1 (+)				-0.740** (0.260)	-0.781** (0.265)
Treatment 2 (-)				-0.042 (0.256)	-0.183 (0.266)
Constant	1.857*** (0.293)	1.469*** (0.266)	1.985*** (0.299)	2.100*** (0.268)	2.838 (1.938)
Controls	No	No	No	No	Yes
Num. obs.	1,803	2,143	1,285	5,231	5,231
Pseudo- R^2 (McFadden)	0.115	0.299	0.122	0.192	0.237
Log Likelihood	-736.40	-809.51	-641.89	-2,210.39	-2,087.09

Notes. This table reports estimates from logistic regressions of the binary choice of whether to allocate the investment to the option carrying the data leak risk on a set of experimental parameters, conditional on the treatment (Models 1–3) and pooled across all treatments (Models 4–5). The sample is restricted to rounds with strictly positive data leak probability and non-negative spreads. Standard errors clustered at the participant level are reported in parentheses. “Probability (Std.)” and “Spread (Std.)” denote standardized values of, respectively, the probability of a data leak associated with the risky allocation option and the difference in expected returns (in percentage points) between the risky and the safe option, in rounds where the risky option weakly dominates in terms of expected return. “Controls” include age, gender, number of children, marital situation, maximum education level, professional category, financial literacy (PCA index), and response precision measures.

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

risk when the expected monetary gain is sufficiently high, indicating that the marginal value they place on privacy protection is often outweighed by return considerations.

Turning to the induced-value treatments, the coefficients on the treatment dummies in Columns (4)–(5) do not support Hypothesis 2. Relative to the baseline condition, participants in the positive induced-value treatment are in fact less likely to choose the leak option (Treatment 1 coefficients around -0.75 , significant at the 1% level), while participants in the negative induced-value treatment do not differ significantly from the baseline once I condition on spread and leak probability. This pattern suggests that, in this setting, the induced-value manipulation does not generate an additional shift in privacy-risk taking beyond that already captured by the experimental parameters themselves.

4.3 Dynamic effects of data leaks

Result 3 (Dynamic effects of data leaks). *Past data leaks affect subsequent allocation decisions primarily through their aggregate, rather than individual, consequences: the number of other participants affected by a leak in the previous round significantly reduces the likelihood of investing in the privacy-risk option, whereas own past leaks have, at best, only modest and short-lived effects.*

Table 4: Determinants of Allocation Choices: Privacy Outcomes

	<i>Dependent variable: Data Leak Allocation</i>				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
First Leak _{t-1}	0.066 (0.114)				
First Leak _{t-1} (Cont.)		-0.216 (0.157)			
Individual Leak _{t-1}			-0.072 (0.115)		0.030 (0.121)
Others Participants' Leaks _{t-1}				-0.040** (0.001)	-0.041** (0.001)
Constant	-1.726*** (0.313)	-1.702*** (0.312)	-1.724*** (0.313)	-1.631*** (0.316)	-1.630*** (0.316)
Experimental Parameters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FE Individuals & Rounds	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Num. obs.	10974	10974	10974	10974	10974
PseudoR ² (McFadden)	0.592	0.592	0.592	0.593	0.593
Log Likelihood	-2987.2	-2985.9	-2987.0	-2983.4	-2983.4

Notes. This table reports estimates from fixed-effects logistic regressions of the binary choice of whether to allocate the investment to the option carrying the data leak risk on a set of privacy consequences derived from the data leak risk present in the experiment. Standard errors clustered at the participant level are reported in parentheses. Experimental parameters include "Probability" which refers to the probability level associated with the risky allocation option and "Spread" which indicates the difference in percentage points between the expected return of the risky and safe allocation option. Despite not being displayed in this table, experimental parameters are standardized and estimates are similar to the ones presented earlier. Both individual and round fixed effects are included.

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

Support: Table 4 reports fixed-effects logit estimates of the probability of allocating to the option carrying the data leak risk, pooling all treatments and controlling for experimental parameters (spread and leak probability), individual fixed effects, and round fixed effects (Models 1–5). The different specifications successively introduce indicators capturing the timing and persistence of individual leaks, as well as the number of leaks experienced by other participants in the previous round.

I first consider the impact of participants' own data leaks. The variable *First Leak*_{t-1} takes value 1 if a participant experienced their first data leak in the previous round and 0 otherwise, and *First Leak*_{t-1} (Cont.) remains equal to 1 in all subsequent rounds once a first leak has occurred. Across Models (1) and (2), neither of these variables is statistically significant, suggesting that neither the immediate local effect of a first leak nor its persistence over later rounds materially changes the probability of choosing the leak option once I condition on individual and round fixed effects and on the financial incentives. Likewise, the indicator *Individual Leak*_{t-1}, which captures any own leak in the previous round (irrespective of whether it is the first), is not significantly

associated with subsequent leak allocations in Models (3) and (5).

By contrast, the variable *Others Participants' Leaks_{t-1}*, defined as the number of other participants in the same session who experienced a data leak in the previous round, is both negative and statistically significant coefficient in Models (4) and (5). This implies that, holding constant the experimental parameters and unobserved individual heterogeneity, an increase in the number of peers affected by a leak in the prior round is associated with a lower propensity to allocate to the option carrying the leak risk. In other words, participants appear to react more strongly to the magnitude of collective leaks than to their own individual experience of a leak. Given the inclusion of rich controls and fixed effects, the magnitude of these coefficients is moderate, but the sign and statistical significance are robust, indicating a “crowd effect” whereby observing (or being informed about) others’ exposures makes participants temporarily more cautious in their privacy-related investment decisions.

Table 5: Determinants of Allocation Choices: Privacy Outcomes (Cont.)

	<i>Dependent variable: Data Leak Allocation</i>					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
First Leak _{t-1}	-0.045 (0.029)		-0.062* (0.030)		-0.088** (0.035)	
First Leak _{t-1} (Cont.)		-0.063** (0.021)		-0.086** (0.025)		-0.155*** (0.030)
Experimental Parameters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FE Individuals	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Num. obs.	1245	1245	946	946	614	614
PseudoR ² (McFadden)	0.747	0.751	0.837	0.842	0.902	0.913
Log Likelihood	-254.1	-250.6	-163.0	-158.8	-97.60	-87.01

Notes. This table reports estimates from fixed-effects logistic regressions of the binary choice of whether to allocate the investment to the option carrying the data leak risk on a set of privacy consequences derived from the data leak risk present in the experiment and conditioned on the event window considered: 4 pre- and post-event rounds in Models 1-2, 3 pre- and post-event rounds in Models 3-4, and 2 pre- and post-event rounds in Models 5-6. Standard errors clustered at the participant level are reported in parentheses. Experimental parameters include “Probability”, which refers to the probability level associated with the risky allocation option, and “Spread”, which indicates the difference in percentage points between the expected return of the risky and safe allocation option. Despite not being displayed in this table, experimental parameters are standardized and estimates are similar to the ones presented earlier. Individual fixed effects are included.

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

To further explore the dynamic impact of individual leaks and to alleviate some of the identification challenges arising in the full panel, I complement this analysis with an event-study design centered around the first leak experienced by each participant. In this approach, the occurrence of the first leak is treated as an event, and I restrict attention to symmetric windows of rounds around that event. Table 5 reports fixed-effects logit estimates for windows of four pre- and post-event rounds (Models 1–2), three pre- and post-event rounds (Models 3–4), and two pre- and post-event rounds (Models 5–6). As before, all specifications control for the experimental parameters and individual fixed effects.

Within the widest event window (four rounds before and after the first leak), the local effect of the first leak, captured by *First Leak_{t-1}*, is not statistically significant (Model 1), whereas

the persistent indicator *First Leakt* – 1 (*Cont.*) is negative and significant (Model 2), indicating that, once the first leak has occurred, participants become less likely to choose the leak option in subsequent rounds. When I narrow the event window to three pre- and post-event rounds (Models 3–4), both the local and persistent measures become statistically significant, with negative coefficients. For the shortest window (two pre- and post-event rounds; Models 5–6), the estimated coefficients on both the local and persistent indicators are again negative and increase in absolute value, suggesting a stronger reduction in leak allocations in the immediate aftermath of the first leak. These patterns indicate that individual leaks do induce a behavioral adjustment away from the risky option in the short run, but that this effect attenuates as I move further away from the event and when the full panel (including rounds without leak risk or with dominated risky options) is considered.

Overall, the panel and event-study evidence point to a nuanced picture of dynamic privacy behavior. On the one hand, aggregate leak events—captured by the number of other participants affected in the previous round—consistently reduce willingness to accept privacy risk, even after controlling for incentives and fixed effects. On the other hand, the impact of own leaks is modest and short-lived, becoming clearly visible only when I zoom in on a narrow window around the first leak. Within the framework of privacy calculus, these findings suggest that while individuals do react to salient privacy shocks, especially when many others are simultaneously affected, these reactions are not strong enough to permanently overturn the dominant role of financial incentives documented in the previous result.

4.4 Individual heterogeneity

I complete the analysis by focusing on the influence of individual characteristics on the behaviors observed in the experiment and provide tentative evidence to verify whether the privacy paradox may arise due to significant informational asymmetry concerning privacy risks and outcomes by including in this analysis the psychometric measures from Dienlin and Trepte (2015). All the Likert scale measures used in the post-experimental survey are described in Table A.3 in the Appendix.

4.4.1 Economic and behavioral characteristics

Result 4 (Economic and behavioral characteristics). *Conditional on experimental parameters and basic demographics, observed economic and behavioral characteristics exhibit only limited explanatory power for allocation decisions: neither digital knowledge nor the proxies for loss and risk aversion significantly predict allocations to the data-leak option, while economic conditions matter only weakly, with a small and imprecise pattern suggesting that participants with significant property assets are more likely to accept leak risks.*

Support: Table 15 reports logit estimates of the probability of allocating to the option carrying the data leak risk on the restricted sample used in Section 4.2.2 (rounds with strictly positive leak probability and non-negative spreads), always controlling for the experimental parameters (spread and leak probability, standardized) and for the full set of socio-demographic and literacy controls.⁹ Columns (1)–(4) add digital knowledge and behavioral proxies for loss and risk aversion; Columns (5)–(6) introduce pre-registered economic characteristics.

Across all specifications, the coefficient on *Digital Knowledge* is small, negative, and statistically insignificant. This suggests that, conditional on the financial incentives and basic demographics, participants’ general digital skills do not translate into systematically different propensities to accept the data leak risk.

Turning to behavioral characteristics, Columns (2)–(4) and (6) introduce measures of *Loss*

Aversion and *Risk Aversion*. The estimated coefficients on these variables are uniformly negative, indicating that more loss- or risk-averse individuals are, if anything, less likely to allocate to the leak option, but they are not statistically significant at conventional levels in any of the reported specifications. Adding the full set of economic variables in Column (6) does not appreciably change these estimates. Overall, I therefore do not find robust evidence that differences in these behavioral measures meaningfully shift the privacy–return trade-off, once I account for the structure of the task and observable demographics.

Columns (5) and (6) focus on economic characteristics that were pre-registered as potential determinants of privacy behavior. Using the lowest income group (0–10k euros) as the reference category, none of the higher income brackets exhibits a statistically significant association with the probability of selecting the leak option. The picture is similar for most economics variables. *Home Ownership*, *Rent*, *Financial Wealth*, *Savings*, and *Indebtedness* all have coefficients fail to reach statistical significance. The only economic characteristic that shows a consistently significant association is *Property Assets*. In both Columns (5) and (6), the coefficient on property assets is positive and statistically significant at the 5% level (0.263 and 0.274, respectively, with s.e. 0.129). This pattern suggests that participants who report owning positive property assets are somewhat more inclined to choose the leak option, conditional on the experimental parameters and other controls. However, the effect remains modest in size.

Taken together, these results indicate that, within the experimental framework, observable economic and behavioral heterogeneity plays only a secondary role in shaping privacy-related allocation decisions. The main drivers of behavior remain the experimental parameters themselves while differences in digital knowledge, loss and risk attitudes, and economic characteristics add little additional explanatory power. From the perspective of the privacy calculus, this suggests that, at least in this controlled setting with immediate privacy outcomes, most participants apply a broadly similar trade-off between monetary returns and privacy risks, irrespective of their economic circumstances or standard behavioral traits.

4.4.2 Psychometric measures and self-reported perceptions

Result 5 (Privacy concerns and self-perceptions). *Ex-post privacy concerns and self-reported attention to the risk of data leaks are negatively associated with choosing the leak option, whereas past personal exposure to data leaks and curiosity about others' leaks show no robust relationship with allocation behavior.*

Support: Table 6 reports logit estimates of the probability of allocating to the option carrying the data leak risk on the same restricted sample as before (rounds with strictly positive leak probability and non–negative spreads), always controlling for the experimental parameters (standardized spread and leak probability) and for the full set of socio-demographic and literacy controls. All psychometric and self-reported variables are measured at the very end of the experiment, after participants have completed the allocation task. The coefficients should therefore be interpreted as correlational patterns between ex post attitudes/perceptions and earlier choices, rather than as clean causal effects.

The first column focuses on a composite *Privacy Concerns* index, constructed using principal component analysis on the ten items from Dienlin and Trepte (2015). In Model (1), the coefficient on this index is negative but only marginally significant (–0.095, s.e. 0.050). When I add the full battery of self-reported perceptions in Model (3), the coefficient becomes slightly larger in magnitude and statistically significant at the 5% level (–0.113, s.e. 0.048). This pattern indicates that participants who score higher on the general privacy concerns factor are less likely to allocate to the leak option, even after conditioning on the financial incentives and individual controls. In

Table 6: Determinants of Allocation Choices: Psychometric and self-reported measures

	<i>Dependent variable: Data Leak Allocation</i>		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
<i>Psychometrics measures</i>			
Privacy Concerns	-0.095 (0.050)		-0.113* (0.048)
<i>Self-reported measures</i>			
Information Accuracy		-0.463** (0.159)	-0.490** (0.152)
Data Leak Experienced		0.098 (0.144)	0.071 (0.138)
Interest in Others' Leaks		0.128 (0.142)	0.221 (0.139)
Perceived Risk		0.170 (0.091)	0.166 (0.090)
Leak Influence		-0.436* (0.170)	-0.387* (0.170)
Increased Awareness		-0.100 (0.159)	-0.161 (0.163)
Constant	-3.426 (4.368)	-0.635 (4.087)	-3.592 (4.170)
<hr/>			
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
<hr/>			
Num. obs.	5231	5231	5231
Log Likelihood	-1642.5	-1620.17	-1613.08
PseudoR ² (McFadden)	0.399	0.408	0.41

Notes. Logistic regressions of the choice to allocate to the data-leak option. The sample is restricted to rounds with strictly positive data-leak probability and non-negative spreads. Standard errors (in parentheses) are clustered at the participant level. Experimental parameters (probability and spread) are included but not reported. “Controls” include age, gender, number of children, marital situation, maximum education level, professional category, financial literacy (PCA index), and response precision measures.

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

other words, ex-post stated privacy concerns are aligned with more privacy-protective behavior within the allocation task.

Columns (2) and (3) then incorporate a set of self-reported measures elicited in the post-experiment questionnaire. *Information Accuracy* captures how precise participants report having been in their questionnaire responses (from “not at all” to “very precise”). Its coefficient is negative and statistically significant across Models (2) and (3) (e.g. -0.490 , s.e. 0.152 in Model (3)), suggesting that participants who claimed to have answered more accurately and carefully are less likely to select the leak option. Similarly, *Leak Influence*, which measures the self-reported extent to which the risk of a data leak affected investment decisions (from “not at all” to “very strongly”), is also negatively associated with choosing the leak option (-0.387 , s.e. 0.170 in Model (3)). These two variables can be viewed as ex post meta-cognitive assessments of how seriously participants took the privacy dimension during the task; their negative coefficients are consistent with the idea that those who report having integrated the risk of leaks into their reasoning are also those who,

in practice, avoided the risky option more often.

By contrast, the remaining self-reported measures do not display robust, statistically significant associations with allocation decisions. Having previously experienced a personal data leak (*Data Leak Experienced*) is not significantly related to the propensity to choose the leak option (coefficient 0.071, s.e. 0.138 in Model (3)), suggesting that prior real-world exposure, as captured by this coarse indicator, does not strongly shape behavior in the experimental environment. Self-reported *Interest in Others' Leaks* during the experiment (from “not at all” to “very strongly”) enters with a positive but non-significant coefficient (0.221, s.e. 0.139).

The coefficient on *Perceived Risk*—how dangerous participants judge the risk of a data leak in this experiment— is positive but only marginally significant (0.166, s.e. 0.090). Given the underlying scale, where higher values correspond to perceiving the leak as less dangerous (shifting from “very dangerous” toward “not dangerous”), this positive sign is consistent with the idea that participants who downplay the danger of data leaks are more likely to choose the leak option. Finally, *Increased Awareness*, which asks whether participants feel more aware of data-leak risks after the experiment (from “not at all” to “extremely”), has a negative but statistically insignificant coefficient, indicating no robust link between ex-post awareness and prior allocation behavior once the other variables are taken into account.

Taken together, the results provide mixed support for the pre-registered hypotheses. For Hypothesis 1 (financial return and leak risk), the evidence in Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2 provides clear support: higher expected-return spreads strongly increase, and higher leak probabilities decrease, the likelihood of choosing the leak option. By contrast, Hypothesis 2 (induced values of privacy risk) is not supported: once I control for spread and leak probability, subjects in the positive induced-value treatment are in fact less likely to choose the leak option than in the baseline, and those in the negative induced-value treatment do not differ significantly. For Hypothesis 3 (personal leaks versus magnitude of leaks), the evidence is mixed: as shown in Section 4.3, the number of other participants affected by a leak in the previous round robustly reduces subsequent investment in the privacy-risk option, whereas own leaks have at best modest and short-lived effects, which become visible only in narrow event windows around the first leak. Finally, Hypothesis 4 (individual heterogeneity) is only partially supported: as discussed in Sections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2, I find little evidence that risk or loss aversion and most economic characteristics systematically shape allocation choices, while a generic privacy-concern index does exhibit a modest but statistically significant association with behavior, contrary to the last part of the hypothesis.

Beyond these hypothesis-by-hypothesis assessments, the contribution of the experiment lies less in “re-establishing” the privacy calculus and more in documenting how it operates in a specific, rich environment: a dynamic setting with instantaneous privacy outcomes, a persistent but ethically constrained leak risk, a sequence of repeated financial–privacy trade-offs, and visible leaks affecting other participants. Within this framework, I show that financial incentives remain the primary driver of behavior, but that they interact in nuanced ways with realized privacy shocks, information about others’ leaks, and ex-post privacy attitudes—a combination that has rarely been examined jointly in a single experimental design.

5 Conclusion

This paper has examined how individuals trade off financial performance against the protection of their own financial data in a dynamic environment with time-varying leak probabilities and instantaneous privacy outcomes. I implemented a repeated investment task in which one option could offer higher expected returns at the cost of an explicit risk that sensitive financial information

would be leaked to peers, while the alternative option was privacy-safe. Within this framework, I combined rich experimental variation in expected returns and leak probabilities with realized leak events and detailed measures of individual characteristics and privacy attitudes.

The first main finding is that participants behave in a way that is broadly consistent with a privacy–return trade-off, even when the data at stake are financial and leak probabilities are fully transparent. Higher spreads in expected returns markedly increase, and higher leak probabilities reduce, the likelihood of choosing the privacy-risky option. However, the estimated elasticities are strongly asymmetric: choices respond much more to changes in expected returns than to changes in leak probabilities. Moreover, the induced-value treatments designed to shift the financial attractiveness of the leak option do not generate the pattern predicted in the pre-analysis plan. If anything, the positive induced-value treatment is associated with a lower propensity to choose the leak option once spread and probability are controlled for, and the negative induced-value treatment does not differ significantly from the baseline. Taken together, these results suggest that, in this benchmark setting with explicit probabilities and immediate consequences, financial incentives are the dominant force shaping behavior, and additional induced-value manipulations add little over and above the structure of payoffs and risks itself.

The second main finding concerns dynamics and social spillovers. Using both panel regressions and an event-study design around the first personal leak, I document that own leaks have only modest and short-lived effects on subsequent choices. Participants temporarily reduce their propensity to choose the leak option after their first leak, but this adjustment attenuates as the window around the event widens and essentially disappears in the full panel once I control for individual and round fixed effects. By contrast, the magnitude of leaks affecting other participants in the previous round robustly predicts behavior: when more peers experience a leak, participants are less likely to choose the privacy-risky option in the next round. This “crowd effect” points to the importance of public signals and social information in privacy-related decision-making, over and above individual experience of harm.

Third, I find only limited evidence that standard measures of economic variables and behavioral traits systematically shape privacy choices in this environment. Risk and loss aversion, digital knowledge, income, and most economic characteristics are not robustly associated with the propensity to choose the leak option once experimental parameters and basic controls are taken into account. By contrast, a generic privacy-concern index (constructed from Dienlin and Trepte (2015)) and a small set of ex post self-reports—such as perceived response accuracy and the self-reported influence of leak risk on decisions—are modestly but consistently aligned with more privacy-protective behavior. These patterns speak to the privacy paradox debate: in this setting with instantaneous privacy outcomes and explicit probabilities, broad attitudinal measures are not completely uninformative, but their predictive power remains small relative to the direct effect of financial incentives and leak probabilities.

From a policy and design perspective, the experiment highlights several points. First, even when probabilities are clearly stated and leaks involve sensitive financial information, many individuals are willing to accept non-trivial increases in leak risk for relatively moderate gains in expected return. This has implications for open banking and finance initiatives: if financial incentives are strong enough, transparency about leak probabilities alone may not suffice to induce conservative behavior. Second, the strong response to aggregate leak events suggests a potential role for public disclosure and breach-notification policies—not only as accountability tools, but also as mechanisms that can temporarily shift demand away from privacy-risky options following salient incidents. Third, the weak role of standard economic and behavioral heterogeneity, combined with the modest but coherent contribution of privacy attitudes, suggests that targeting interventions solely on the basis of observable characteristics may be difficult, and that context-specific communication about

risks may matter more than generic awareness campaigns.

Naturally, these conclusions come with limitations. The laboratory environment involves ethically constrained leaks to a small group of peers, not to the wider public or to firms, and the stakes, while salient, are modest compared to those associated with major real-world financial breaches. The sample is relatively young and educated, and the task abstracts from many forms of uncertainty and opacity present in actual data ecosystems. In that sense, the behavior observed here should be viewed as an upper bound on the extent to which individuals can engage in a transparent privacy calculus when probabilities are known and outcomes are immediate.

Future work could relax some of these constraints and explore complementary dimensions of privacy decision-making. One natural extension is to introduce ambiguity over leak probabilities or over the future uses of leaked data, to examine how ambiguity attitudes interact with financial incentives. Another is to vary the audience and consequences of leaks, for instance, leaks to firms, employers, or platforms rather than to anonymous peers, and to study how this affects the perceived cost of disclosure. Finally, combining dynamic leak environments with richer social structures and long-run outcomes could help bridge the gap between stylized experimental settings and the complex, evolving data ecosystems of the digital economy.

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Notes

¹European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) (2023), *ENISA Threat Landscape 2023*, ENISA, October 19, 2023. Available at <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-threat-landscape-2023>.

²See pre-analysis plan at <https://aspredicted.org/x5vf-jhkd.pdf>.

³See the full instructions in Table 10.

⁴<https://www.parisschoolofeconomics.eu/fr/connaitre-pse/engagements-ethiques/integrite-scientifique/irb-institutional-review-board/>

⁵<https://leep.univ-paris1.fr/accueil.htm>

⁶Directive 2014/65/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 on markets in financial instruments.

⁷<https://europa.eu/europass/fr>

⁸At the end of December 2023, the EUR–USD exchange rate was approximately 1 USD = 0.9 EUR.

⁹As in previous tables, the coefficients on the experimental parameters are not reported but remain very similar in sign and magnitude to those presented earlier.

¹⁰<https://www.parisschoolofeconomics.eu/en/about/ethics/scientific-integrity/institutional-review-board>

¹¹<https://aspredicted.org>

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Appendix

A Experimental Design Appendices

A.1 Decision Interface

Figure 5: Decision Interface

Allocation Decision [4/60]

	Option A			Option B		
Risk of data leak	No risk			40%		
Scenarios	Unfavorable	Realistic	Favorable	Unfavorable	Realistic	Favorable
Probability	(25%)	(50%)	(25%)	(25%)	(50%)	(25%)
Yield	-4%	12%	32%	-8%	8%	28%
Expected Return	13%			9%		
Spread	4 percentage points					
Allocation decision	<input type="radio"/> A <input type="radio"/> B					

Allocation amount

You have an endowment of **100,00** ECUs.

Specify the amount you wish to allocate in the option chosen above.

A.2 Additional Tasks

Figure 6: Risk Aversion Elicitation Task à la Holt & Laury (2002)

Initial Task No. 1

In this task, for each row you must choose between two lotteries, A and B, that are offered to you. Lottery A is characterized by a reward of 2 euros or 1.60 euros along with the associated probabilities for each reward, and lottery B is characterized by a reward of 3.85 euros or 0.10 euros along with the associated probabilities for each reward.

You have 10 choices to make (between A and B), one for each row. The amounts for the different lotteries will always be the same, but the probabilities will change. The lower you go in the table, the higher the probability associated with the larger reward.

Your reward will be determined by the random selection of one of the rows, and, depending on your choice, by the outcome of the lottery you selected.

#	A			B				
1	1/10th of 2,0€	or	9/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	1/10th of 3,85€	or	9/10th of 0,1€
2	2/10th of 2,0€	or	8/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	2/10th of 3,85€	or	8/10th of 0,1€
3	3/10th of 2,0€	or	7/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	3/10th of 3,85€	or	7/10th of 0,1€
4	4/10th of 2,0€	or	6/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	4/10th of 3,85€	or	6/10th of 0,1€
5	5/10th of 2,0€	or	5/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	5/10th of 3,85€	or	5/10th of 0,1€
6	6/10th of 2,0€	or	4/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	6/10th of 3,85€	or	4/10th of 0,1€
7	7/10th of 2,0€	or	3/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	7/10th of 3,85€	or	3/10th of 0,1€
8	8/10th of 2,0€	or	2/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	8/10th of 3,85€	or	2/10th of 0,1€
9	9/10th of 2,0€	or	1/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	9/10th of 3,85€	or	1/10th of 0,1€
10	10/10th of 2,0€	or	0/10th of 1,6€	<input type="radio"/> A	<input type="radio"/> B	10/10th of 3,85€	or	0/10th of 0,1€

Continue

Figure 7: Proportion of safe choices in each decision (Holt & Laury (2002))

Notes. Data represent the average choice probabilities (solid line with dots) alongside the risk-neutral prediction (dashed line). 40 of 186 participants (21.5%) exhibited internally inconsistent choice patterns—an inconsistency rate comparable to that commonly reported in standard risk-elicitation protocols.

Figure 8: Loss Aversion Elicitation Task à la Gächter et al. (2022)

Initial Task No. 2

In the following table, you will find a list of coin toss games with different rewards. **The rewards differ depending on the amount you lose if the coin lands on heads or tails.** For each row, you must indicate whether you refuse or accept to toss the coin.

To determine your payment, one of the six rows will be selected at random. If you indicated that you wanted to toss the coin for the randomly selected row, the coin toss will be performed and will determine your winnings or losses.

#

1	If the coin lands on heads, you lose 2€ ; if it lands on tails, you win 6€ .	<input type="radio"/> Refuser	<input type="radio"/> Acceptor
2	If the coin lands on heads, you lose 3€ ; if it lands on tails, you win 6€ .	<input type="radio"/> Refuser	<input type="radio"/> Acceptor
3	If the coin lands on heads, you lose 4€ ; if it lands on tails, you win 6€ .	<input type="radio"/> Refuser	<input type="radio"/> Acceptor
4	If the coin lands on heads, you lose 5€ ; if it lands on tails, you win 6€ .	<input type="radio"/> Refuser	<input type="radio"/> Acceptor
5	If the coin lands on heads, you lose 6€ ; if it lands on tails, you win 6€ .	<input type="radio"/> Refuser	<input type="radio"/> Acceptor
6	If the coin lands on heads, you lose 7€ ; if it lands on tails, you win 6€ .	<input type="radio"/> Refuser	<input type="radio"/> Acceptor

Continue

Table 7: Acceptance Behavior by Lottery Choice Category

Lottery Choice Category	N	%
Reject All Lotteries	7	3.8
Accept #1; Reject #2–#6	24	12.9
Accept #1–#2; Reject #3–#6	63	33.9
Accept #1–#3; Reject #4–#6	51	27.4
Accept #1–#4; Reject #5–#6	19	10.2
Accept #1–#5; Reject #6	9	4.8
Accept All Lotteries	13	7.0
Inconsistent Choice Patterns	22	11.8

A.3 Questionnaires

Question	Possible answer(s)
Socio-demographic questions	
What is your age?	<i>Numeric</i>
What is your gender?	Male Female Non-binary Prefer not to say
What is your marital status?	Single Cohabiting Married Divorced Widowed Prefer not to say
Do you have any dependent children?	None 1 child 2 children 3 or more children Prefer not to say
Which occupational category best describes you?	Farmer Artisan/merchant/business owner Executive/professional Intermediate profession Employee Worker Student Retired Other
What is your highest level of education completed?	Primary or no formal education Secondary Bachelor's degree or BTS Master's degree Doctorate
Economic Information	
What is the postal code of your tax residence?	<i>Numeric</i>
What is your net annual salary?	0–10 000 € 10,000–25,000€ 25,000–45,000€ 45,000–60,000€ 60,000–100,000€

	Over 100,000€
Are you the owner of your primary residence, or do you live with parents who own theirs?	Yes No
What is the amount of your rent? (0 if you own or live with parents who own.)	<i>Numeric</i>
What is the estimated value of your real estate assets (or your family's if you are a student)?	<i>Numeric</i>
What is the estimated value of your financial assets (or your family's if you are a student)?	<i>Numeric</i>
How much are you able to save each month?	<i>Numeric</i>
Do you currently have any loans?	Yes No
What is the estimated total of your loans? (0 if none.)	<i>Numeric</i>
Financial Knowledge & Experience	
If you wanted to invest now, what would be the primary goal of your investment?	Grow my savings Prepare a major purchase Save for emergencies Plan for retirement
If you wanted to invest now, what would be your investment horizon?	Less than 5 years 5–10 years 10–15 years More than 15 years
“A high expected return implies a high risk of capital loss.” Do you believe this statement is true?	True False I don't know
What is the name of the payment a company makes to its shareholders?	Dividend Interest Profit I don't know
“The more volatile a financial asset is. . .”	The riskier it is The less risky it is I don't know
What is a share (stock)?	A property title A debt title An investment fund

	I don't know
Have you ever experienced losses on your financial investments?	No Yes, up to 10% Yes, up to 20% Yes, more than 20%
If your investment loses 10% of its value in 3 months, what would you do?	Reinvest to seize the opportunity Hold without panicking Sell some to limit losses Sell all I don't know
Have you ever placed money in a life insurance contract, a brokerage account, or an equity savings plan (PEA)?	Yes No

Table 8: Preliminary questionnaire

Table 9: Digital Knowledge and Privacy Measures

Question	Possible answer(s)
Digital Knowledge (EuroPass)	
I know how to verify that a website asking for personal data is secure (e.g., https, security badge).	I don't know how to do this I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.
When faced with a technical problem, I can find solutions on the Internet.	I don't know how to do this I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.
I know how to use online learning tools to improve my digital skills (e.g., video tutorials, online courses).	I don't know how to do this I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.

I know how to protect myself from unwanted or malicious messages online (e.g., spam, phishing emails).	<p>I don't know how to do this</p> <p>I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.</p>
I know how to copy and move files (documents, images, videos, etc.) between folders, devices, or cloud storage.	<p>I don't know how to do this</p> <p>I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.</p>
I know how to create a profile in various digital environments for personal or professional purposes.	<p>I don't know how to do this</p> <p>I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.</p>
I know how to create and edit digital text files (e.g., Word, OpenDocument, Google Docs).	<p>I don't know how to do this</p> <p>I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.</p>
When using a search engine, I can take advantage of its advanced features.	<p>I don't know how to do this</p> <p>I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.</p>
I know how to use advanced features in a video-conference (e.g., moderation, recording).	<p>I don't know how to do this</p> <p>I can do it with help I can do it by myself I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.</p>
I know how to create new things by combining different types of content (e.g., text and images).	<p>I don't know how to do this</p> <p>I can do it with help I can do it by myself</p>

I can do it confidently and, if necessary, guide others.

Privacy Psychometrics Measures (Dienlin & Trepte, 2015)

Informational Privacy

How much personally identifying information have you already posted on your social networks?

None
Very little
A little
Moderate
Average
High
Very high

How much personally identifying information can generally be found about you on your social networks?

None
Very little
A little
Moderate
Average
High
Very high

How accurately can strangers identify you on your social networks?

None
Very little
A little
Moderate
Average
High
A lot

How much personally identifying information do you currently want to share on your social networks?

None
Very low
Low
Moderate
Average
High
Very high

How much personally identifying information would you generally like to see on your social networks?

None
Very low
Low
Moderate

	Average High Very high
How accurately would you like to be identifiable by strangers on your social networks?	None Very low Low Moderate Average High Very high
I think sharing identifying information on my social networks is:	Not useful Slightly useful Rather not useful Neutral Rather useful Useful Very useful
I think sharing identifying information on my social networks is:	Very disadvantageous Disadvantageous Rather disadvantageous Neutral Rather advantageous Advantageous Very advantageous
I think sharing identifying information on my social networks is:	Very worrying Worrying Rather worrying Neutral Rather reassuring Reassuring Very reassuring
I think sharing identifying information on my social networks is:	Very dangerous Dangerous Rather dangerous Neutral Rather not dangerous Slightly dangerous Not dangerous
I think sharing identifying information on my social networks is:	Very imprudent

	Imprudent Rather imprudent Neutral Rather not imprudent Slightly imprudent Not imprudent
I think sharing identifying information on my social networks is:	Very bad Bad Rather bad Neutral Rather good Good Very good
Social Privacy	
To what extent do you currently limit access to your social network profiles?	Not at all Very little A little Moderately Average A lot Extremely
To what extent is the visibility of your social network content restricted?	Not at all Very little A little Moderately Average A lot Extremely
To what extent are your social network profiles restricted for specific people?	Not at all Very little A little Moderately Average A lot Extremely
To what extent would you like to restrict access to your social network profiles currently?	Not at all Very little A little Moderately Average

	A lot Extremely
To what extent would you like the visibility of your social network content to be limited?	Not at all Very little A little Moderately Average A lot Extremely
To what extent would you like access to your social network profiles restricted for certain people?	Not at all Very little A little Moderately Average A lot Extremely
I think restricting access to one's social profile is:	Not useful Slightly useful Rather not useful Neutral Rather useful Useful Very useful
I think restricting access to one's social profile is:	Very disadvantageous Disadvantageous Rather disadvantageous Neutral Rather advantageous Advantageous Very advantageous
I think restricting access to one's social profile is:	Very worrying Worrying Rather worrying Neutral Rather reassuring Reassuring Very reassuring
I think restricting access to one's social profile is:	Very unpleasant

	Unpleasant Rather unpleasant Neutral Rather not unpleasant Slightly unpleasant Not unpleasant
I think restricting access to one's social profile is:	Very mean Mean Rather mean Neutral Rather fair Fair Very fair
I think restricting access to one's social profile is:	Very bad Bad Rather bad Neutral Rather good Good Very good
Psychological Privacy	
To what extent do you share personal things on your social networks?	Very impersonal Rather impersonal Slightly impersonal Neutral Slightly personal Rather personal Very personal
How accurately do your social network profiles reflect your personality?	Very impersonal Rather impersonal Slightly impersonal Neutral Slightly personal Rather personal Very personal
To what extent are your social network profiles personal?	Very impersonal Rather impersonal Slightly impersonal Neutral Slightly personal

	Rather personal Very personal
How much personal information do you wish to communicate on your social networks?	None Very low Low Moderate Average High Very high
To what extent do you want your social network profiles to resemble your full personality?	Not at all Very little A little Moderately Average A lot Extremely
To what extent do you want your social network profiles to be personal?	Not at all Very little A little Moderately Average A lot Extremely
I think sharing personal information on social networks is:	Not useful Slightly useful Rather not useful Neutral Rather useful Useful Very useful
I think sharing personal information on social networks is:	Very disadvantageous Disadvantageous Rather disadvantageous Neutral Rather advantageous Advantageous Very advantageous
I think sharing personal information on social networks is:	Very worrying Worrying

	<p>Rather worrying Neutral Rather reassuring Reassuring Very reassuring</p>
I think sharing personal information on social networks is:	<p>Very dangerous Dangerous Rather dangerous Neutral Rather not dangerous Slightly dangerous Not dangerous</p>
I think sharing personal information on social networks is:	<p>Very unpleasant Unpleasant Rather unpleasant Neutral Rather not unpleasant Slightly unpleasant Not unpleasant</p>
I think sharing personal information on social networks is:	<p>Very bad Bad Rather bad Neutral Rather good Good Very good</p>
Privacy Concerns	
In general, how concerned are you about your privacy when using the Internet?	<p>Very strongly Strongly Moderately A little Not at all</p>
Are you concerned that online organizations are not who they claim to be?	<p>Very strongly Strongly Moderately A little Not at all</p>
Are you concerned that you are asked for too much personal information when registering or shopping online?	<p>Very strongly</p>

	Strongly Moderately A little Not at all
Are you concerned about online identity theft?	Very strongly Strongly Moderately A little Not at all
Are you concerned that people online are not who they claim to be?	Very strongly Strongly Moderately A little Not at all
Are you concerned that information about you could be found on an old computer?	Very strongly Strongly Moderately A little Not at all
Are you concerned that strangers might obtain personal information about you from your on-line activities?	Very strongly Strongly Moderately A little Not at all
Are you concerned that a message you send on-line might be read by someone other than its intended recipient?	Very strongly Strongly Moderately A little Not at all
Are you concerned that messages you receive online might not come from the person they claim to be?	Very strongly Strongly Moderately A little Not at all

Specific Privacy Behaviors

On my social networks, I use my real first name (exactly as on my passport).	No Yes
On my social networks, I use my real last name (exactly as on my passport).	No Yes
On my social networks, I display my current address.	No Yes
On my social networks, I display my phone number even when it is not required.	No Yes
Have you ever posted a religious, political, or ethical statement on social networks?	No Yes
How often do you post on social networks?	Never Once every few months Once a month Several times a month Several times a week Once a day Several times a day
Feedback Items	
During this experiment, how accurate were the questionnaire responses you provided?	Not at all A little Moderately Precise Very precise
Have you ever experienced a personal data leak?	Yes, once Yes, several times No
During this experiment, were you interested in other participants' data leaks?	Not at all A little Moderately Strongly Very strongly
How would you characterize the risk of a data leak in this experiment?	Very dangerous Dangerous Rather dangerous

	Neutral
	Rather not dangerous
	Slightly dangerous
	Not dangerous
Did the risk of a data leak influence your investment decisions?	Not at all
	A little
	Moderately
	Strongly
	Very strongly
Are you more aware of potential risks associated with data leaks after participating in this experiment?	Not at all
	Slightly
	Moderately
	Strongly
	Extremely

A.4 Instructions

Thank you for your participation!

You are about to participate in a decision-making study. Each participant receives exactly the same instructions. All decisions and interactions are anonymous.

It is important that you remain silent and do not communicate in any way with other participants outside of your interactions in the experimental interface. If you have any questions, please raise your hand and I will come to answer them personally.

You will be paid in cash at the end of the experiment; your earnings will depend on your decisions and chance.

Remuneration:

- All participants earn a fixed payment of €5 for their participation.
- You will receive additional compensation for three experimental tasks: two initial tasks and one main experimental task. Payments for these tasks will be communicated at the end of the experimental session.
- Total compensation will be the sum of your fixed payment and your payments for the three tasks.
- The two initial tasks will be performed and remunerated directly in euros.
- The main experimental task will be conducted using experimental monetary units called ECUs. ECUs earned will be converted at a rate of 12.5ECUs per €1.

Instructions for the main task:

Allocation In each decision interface you will have an allocation of 100 ECUs.

Investment choice You must choose to invest in either Option A or Option B. Both options involve risky investment opportunities.

Investment amount You will be asked to enter the amount you wish to invest in the chosen option. Any units not invested will be added to your potential gains or losses.

Investment scenarios Each option is characterized by three scenarios, with probabilities displayed in the interface:

- 25% chance of a favorable scenario,
- 50% chance of a realistic scenario,
- 25% chance of an unfavorable scenario.

The scenario implemented will determine the corresponding payoff. Probabilities remain constant, but payoffs may change across interfaces.

Expected payoff The interface shows the expected payoff (the average return) for each option.

Payoff difference The interface also shows the difference in expected payoff between the two options, in percentage points.

Risk Both Option A and Option B have the same volatility (financial risk).

Probability of data leak One option is randomly assigned a probability of personal data leak:

- If Option A has a leak probability, Option B does not, and vice versa—this assignment is common to all participants.
- Leak probabilities are independent of expected payoffs and vary randomly from 0% to 40% in 5% increments.

Data leak outcome A leak occurs if the random draw falls below the leak probability. The result page will display leaked personal data (age and pseudonym plus two randomly chosen economic variables) for all participants whose chosen option experienced a leak.

Result page Your decision outcomes will appear on a result page once all participants have decided.

Number of decisions You will face 60 decision interfaces. One of your 60 decisions will be randomly selected for payment.

Summary of instructions:

- Choose between Option A and Option B.
 - One option is randomly assigned a probability of personal data leak.
 - You can navigate only by using the “Continue” button; you cannot return to a previous page.
 - The experiment should take approximately 1h30.
- Before the main experimental phase, you will be shown an example decision interface summarizing all information.

Technical note: All participants must complete each decision for the server to generate the result page.

Table 10: Instructions

B Additional Results

Table 11: Summary Statistics of Continuous Variables

	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
Age	28.2	7.6	19.0	26.0	52.0
<i>Economic Variables</i>					
Rent	466.9	479.1	0.0	453.5	3750.0
Property Asset	126355.6	226042.6	0.0	462.5	1300000.0
Financial Wealth	39779.1	121760.3	0.0	7500.0	1000000.0
Savings	217.5	276.8	0.0	100.0	1200.0
Indebtedness	7386.2	28955.8	0.0	0.0	200000.0
<i>Consistency Ratios</i>					
Not Included in Leaks	96.4	8.5	42.9	100.0	100.0
Included in Leaks	82.5	15.1	25.0	87.5	100.0

Table 12: Summary Statistics of Categorical Variables

		N	%
<i>Gender</i>	Women	91	48.9
	Men	95	51.1
<i>Marital</i>	Single	148	79.6
	In a relationship	22	11.8
	Divorced	2	1.1
	Married	11	5.9
	Prefer not to answer	3	1.6
<i>Children</i>	1 child	7	3.8
	2 children	5	2.7
	3 children or more	3	1.6
	None	170	91.4
	Prefer not to answer	1	0.5
<i>Socio-professional status</i>	Craftsperson, shopkeeper, and business owner	7	3.8
	Other	10	5.4
	Executive and higher intellectual profession	20	10.8
	Employee	31	16.7
	Student	106	57.0
	Intermediate profession	12	6.5
<i>Education</i>	PhD	3	1.6
	Bachelor's degree or Advanced Technician's Certificate	68	36.6
	Master's degree	83	44.6
	Primary or no education	2	1.1
	Secondary education	30	16.1
<i>Annual Salary</i>	0-10 000 euros	105	56.5
	10 000-25 000 euros	30	16.1
	25 000-45 000 euros	42	22.6
	45 000-60 000 euros	6	3.2
	60 000-100 000 euros	2	1.1
	More than 100 000 euros	1	0.5

Table 13: Summary Statistics of Data included in Data Leaks

Measure	Pre-registration Questionnaire	Experimental Questionnaire	95% CI	<i>p</i> -value
Annual Salary (Cat.)	1.81	1.79	[−0.190; 0.243]	0.808
Homeownership (Yes or No)	0.278	0.288	[−0.102; 0.081]	0.819
Rent (Cont.)	471.73	466.81	[−92.31; 102.15]	0.921
Property Asset (Cont.)	121693.9	125679.9	[−50601.70; 42629.56]	0.867
Financial Asset (Cont.)	32797.94	39673.32	[−29675.04; 15924.28]	0.553
Savings (Cont.)	218.30	218.98	[−59.46; 58.10]	0.982
Indebted (Yes or No)	0.171	0.155	[−0.059; 0.091]	0.676
Indebtedness (Cont.)	10749.87	7346.68	[−5763.51; 12569.88]	0.465

Table 14: Consistency of responses between pre-registration and experimental questionnaire

Measure	Mean	Standard Deviation
Overall	82.55%	0.151
Annual Salary (Cat.)	89.84%	0.303
Homeownership (Yes or No)	93.58%	0.246
Rent (Cont.)	80.21%	0.399
Property Asset (Cont.)	72.19%	0.449
Financial Asset (Cont.)	63.10%	0.484
Indebted (Yes or No)	97.33%	0.162
Indebtedness (Cont.)	90.37%	0.296

Table 15: Determinants of Allocation Choices: Economic and Behavioral Characteristics

	<i>Dependent variable: Data Leak Allocation</i>					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Digital Knowledge	-0.046 (0.036)	-0.043 (0.036)	-0.053 (0.036)	-0.049 (0.036)	-0.034 (0.038)	-0.031 (0.038)
<i>Behavioral characteristics</i>						
Loss Aversion		-0.129 (0.085)		-0.106 (0.112)		-0.150 (0.112)
Risk Aversion			-0.093 (0.087)	-0.041 (0.108)		-0.022 (0.108)
<i>Economic characteristics (pre-registered)</i>						
Income: 0–10k					Ref.	Ref.
10–25k euros					-0.143 (0.298)	0.014 (0.298)
25–45k euros					-0.084 (0.412)	0.017 (0.412)
45–60k euros					-0.360 (0.650)	-0.474 (0.650)
60–100k euros					-0.058 (0.603)	0.349 (0.603)
>100k euros					-0.973 (0.817)	-1.401 (0.817)
Homeowner					-0.351 (0.280)	-0.314 (0.280)
Rent					0.063 (0.113)	0.044 (0.113)
Property assets					0.263* (0.129)	0.274* (0.129)
Financial wealth					-0.035 (0.057)	-0.059 (0.057)
Savings					0.051 (0.136)	0.089 (0.136)
Indebtedness					0.149 (0.174)	0.071 (0.174)
Constant	2.928 (1.951)	3.473 (2.017)	3.582 (2.280)	3.543 (2.236)	3.470 (1.959)	3.991* (1.959)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Num. obs.	5231	5231	5231	5231	5231	5231
Log likelihood	-2080.06	-2070.16	-2068.73	-2062.97	-2059.81	-2043.02
Pseudo R ² (McFadden)	0.239	0.243	0.244	0.246	0.247	0.253

Notes. Logistic regressions of the choice to allocate to the data-leak option. The sample is restricted to rounds with strictly positive data-leak probability and non-negative spreads. Standard errors (in parentheses) are clustered at the participant level. Experimental parameters (probability and spread) are included but not reported. Controls include age, gender, number of children, marital status, education, professional category, financial literacy (PCA index), and response precision.

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$